

APPLICATIONS OF DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS TO PROBLEMS IN NATURAL SCIENCES

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Annotation. *Mathematical models have long been very successfully used in mechanics, physics, and astronomy. In the modern period, the role of mathematical methods in natural science is increasing. They are now widely used in both biology and chemistry. Mathematical models are also successfully applied here. This article contains some of these applications.*

Keywords. *mathematical model, first-order differential equations, Newton's law of cooling (cooling problem), radioactive decay problem, mixture problem (concentration problem)*

Аннотация. *Математические модели давно и весьма успешно применяются в механике, физике, астрономии. В современный период роль математических методов в естествознании все возрастает. Они теперь широко используются и в биологии, и в химии. Здесь также успешно применяются математические модели. Данная статья содержит некоторые из этих применений.*

Ключевые слова. *математическая модель, дифференциальные уравнения первого порядка, задача об охлаждении тела, задача о радиоактивном распаде, задача о концентрации раствора.*

Annotatsiya. *Matematik modellar uzoq vaqtlardan beri mexanika, fizika va astronomiyada juda muvaffaqiyatli qo'llanilib kelinmoqda. Hozirgi davrda esa tabiatshunoslikda ham matematik usullarning roli ortib bormoqda. Ular hozir biologiyada ham, kimyoda ham keng qo'llaniladi. Ushbu maqolada ulardan ba'zilar keltiriladi.*

Kalit so'zlar. *matematik model, birinchi tartibli differensial tenglamalar, jismning sovishi haqidagi masala, radioaktiv yemirilish haqidagi masala, eritma konsentratsiyasi haqidagi masala.*

The role of mathematics in various fields of natural science has varied historically and over time. It has been shaped by two key factors: the level of development of the mathematical apparatus and the degree of maturity of knowledge regarding the object of study – specifically, the ability to describe its main features and properties using mathematical concepts and relations, or, as it is commonly phrased today, the ability to construct a "mathematical model" of the object.

Let us consider a simple example of a mathematical model. Suppose we need to determine the floor area of a room. To do this, we measure the length and width of the room and then multiply the resulting numbers. This elementary procedure essentially means that the real object – the floor – is replaced by an abstract mathematical model: a rectangle. Dimensions obtained from measurements are assigned to the rectangle, and its area is approximately taken as the required area.

A mathematical model, being based on certain simplifications and idealizations, is never identical to the object under consideration; it does not convey all its properties and nuances but serves as an approximate reflection. However, by replacing a real object with its corresponding model, it becomes possible to formulate the study of the object mathematically and use a

mathematical apparatus that is independent of the specific nature of the object. This apparatus allows for a uniform description of a wide range of facts and observations, detailed quantitative analysis, and the ability to predict how the object will behave under various conditions – thereby forecasting future results.

Mathematical models have long been successfully applied in mechanics, physics, and astronomy. In the modern era, the role of mathematical methods in natural sciences is increasing, and they are now widely used in biology and chemistry. This article contains several such applications.

Let us examine a few examples of applying first-order differential equations with separable variables to problems in natural sciences. To solve most problems, the first step is to derive a differential equation (DE) based on a physical law, and the second step is to classify the resulting equation (linear, separable, etc.) to select the appropriate integration method.

Problem 1. (Cooling of a Body). The rate of cooling of a body in the air is proportional to the difference between the temperature of the body and the air temperature. The air temperature is 20°C . It is known that within 20 minutes, the body cools from 100°C to 60°C . Determine the law of temperature change Θ as a function of time t .

Solution: According to the conditions of the problem:

$$\frac{d\Theta}{dt} = k(\Theta - 20)$$

where k is the proportionality constant. Separating variables and integrating, we get:

$$\frac{d\Theta}{\Theta - 20} = k dt \quad \text{or} \quad \ln(\Theta - 20) = kt + \ln C$$

which, after exponentiation, yields:

$$\Theta - 20 = Ce^{kt}$$

and therefore:

$$\Theta = 20 + Ce^{kt}$$

To determine C , we use the initial condition: at $t = 0$, $\Theta = 100$. Hence, $C = 80$. Thus:

$$\Theta = 20 + 80e^{kt}$$

We determine the coefficient k from the additional condition: at $t = 20$, $\Theta = 60$. Thus:

$$60 = 20 + 80e^{20k} \quad \text{or} \quad e^{20k} = \frac{1}{2}$$

which leads to $e^k = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{1/20}$.

Final function: $\Theta = 20 + 80 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{t/20}$.

Problem 2. (Radioactive Decay). The rate of decay of radium at any moment is proportional to its present mass. Find the law of radium decay if it is known that at the initial moment $t=0$, there were m_0 grams of radium, and the half-life of radium is 1590 years.

Solution: Let x be the mass of radium at time t . Then the rate of decay is:

$$-\frac{dx}{dt} = kx$$

where k is the proportionality constant. Separating variables and integrating gives:

$$x = C \cdot e^{-kt}$$

Using the initial condition (at $t = 0$ m_0), we find $C = m_0$, so:

$$x = m_0 \cdot e^{-kt}$$

We find k using the half-life condition: at $t=1590$, $x = \frac{m_0}{2}$.

$$\frac{m_0}{2} = m_0 \cdot e^{-1950k} \text{ or } e^{1950k} = 2.$$

and therefore: $e^k = 2^{\frac{1}{1950}}$. Final function: $x = m_0 \cdot 2^{-t/1950}$.

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